

The Coupling Constant Series and the Higgs Field

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constant equation, and in particular the difference in the number of terms in the first element, and the second element, it is possible to intersect the Higgs field as a the cause to the difference. The intersection comes to an agreement with the difference between massless gluons of the strong interaction, and positive mass gauge bosons of the weak interaction. The difference is due to an additional term in the primordial coupling series, the Majestic (3).

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Let us look at the first term describing the strong. We saw that the eight vanish since it's An even in our framework.

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1) \quad (2)$$

We also know that from physics the gluons are massless. Let us examine the second term.

$$(24 + (3)) + 3 \quad (3)$$

We know that the bosons that mediate the weak interaction do carry mass. Moreover, we know that the symmetry of SU(2) forbids mass terms in the Lagrangian, and the solution which allows us to include mass terms without ruining the symmetry is the Higgs idea. This idea works by including extra terms. In our framework, the **extra term is the Majestic (3)**. Therefore, the Higgs field is responsible for the lack of order in our series, which could have been a beautiful series of eight multiples. In a sense of the standard model, we can say it is "breaking the symmetry" by inserting the invariant (3).

So overall, we move from spin 0 – perfect clusters of variations. With the Majestic (3) Inserted by the Higgs Field we move to a matter with Spin one-half, we did so by setting the equation on the critical line of the primes. This (3) is really a destabilizing factor than yields a net variation, which is prime as well.

For example – Electromagnetism:

Perfect clusters of variations $\rightarrow 2N$

Destabilize the perfect $2N$ is the Majestic (3) $\rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \rightarrow$ electron.

Blends in the potential cluster to yield in that case $\rightarrow 123$.

The result is the net variation, which is also prime: $N(V) \rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \rightarrow +(5)$

The overall frame yields:

$$\left[2N + \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)\right] + \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \rightarrow \mathbf{123 + 5 = 128.}$$
 Probability of Boson emission.

The main idea of this short paper is that the Majestic (3) is a result of the Higgs field. It is the reason the majestic (3) appears and so, the gauge bosons of the weak interaction are not massless, compared to the previous interaction, where the (3) is not there. So overall, our framework does not contradict the Higgs Idea but support it and allow us an additional view on how the mechanism work. As the Higgs is responsible for additional terms in the Lagrangian, and in the 8-theory we see that the first elements in the series of coupling constant differ by an additional Term, the Majestic (3) or spin $\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)